

iPhone SE 2022 Setup

Date of Setup: 24th January 2024

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Basic steps (pictures on the next slide)

- Pressing home button to choose language
 - Picked language: English
- Selecting country/region
 - Selected: Germany (already preselected)
- Choosing size and font of text
 - Default options retained
- Setup with other phone?
 - Opted not to
- Keyboard instructions
 - No customisation

Screenshots are not possible during the setup process, pictures taken with other phone

Deutsch >

Français >

Nederlands >

Italiano >

Español >

Русский >

English >

Select Your Country or Region

Germany >

More Countries and Regions

Afghanistan >

Åland Islands >

Albania >

Algeria >

< Back

Appearance

Choose the size of text and icons on iPhone.

Continue

Quick Start

⚙️ Looking for nearby devices...

Bring your current iPhone or iPad near this iPhone to sign in and set up.

If your other iPhone or iPad doesn't show options for setting up this iPhone, make sure it's running iOS 11 or later, and has Bluetooth turned on. You can also set up this iPhone manually.

[Set Up Without Another Device](#)

Written and Spoken Languages

The following languages are commonly used in your region. You can set up your iPhone to use these settings or customise them individually.

Preferred Languages

English
German

Keyboards

English (UK)
Deutsch (Deutschland)
Emoji

[Continue](#)

[Customise Settings](#)

Choosing Wi-Fi network

- Picked the university Wi-Fi („eduroam“)
 - Logging in with student access
 - Asked to trust Wi-Fi network → „trust“

Data & Privacy

- Learn more: Offers specific information also offered on the website
- Continue

Set Up iPhone

- Set up for myself
- Not setting up Touch ID
- Creating passcode 123456
- Asked if to transfer apps and Data → dont transfer anything

Setting up Apple ID

Screenshots of Apple ID creation on following slides

- Dont have apple ID → set up anew
 - Create a free Apple ID
 - Name: DICE HHU
 - Date of birth: 10th April 2000
- Asked for E-Mail adress → get an iCloud E-Mail
 - dicephoneproject01@icloud.com
- Setting up Apple ID Password
 - Registration26.01
- Verification by phone number: my private phone number
 - Verification via text message

No SIM 06:25

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Email Address

Email dicephoneproject01@icloud.com

This will be your new Apple ID.

[Use an existing email address](#)

Announcements

Receive Apple emails and communications including announcements, marketing,

Create "dicephoneproject01@icloud.com"?
Make sure this address looks just how you want it to.
You can't change this email address after creating it.

[Create Email Address](#)

[Cancel](#)

No SIM 06:26

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Apple ID Password

Password required

Verify retype password

The password must be at least 8 characters, include a number, an uppercase letter and a lowercase letter.

[Continue](#)

q w e r t y u i o p
a s d f g h j k l
↑ z x c v b n m ⊗
123 globe space return

No SIM 06:27

< Back

Phone Number

Please enter a phone number that can be used to verify your identity via text message or phone call.

+49 (Germany) >

phone number

VERIFY USING:

Text message

Phone call

[Continue](#)

Terms and conditions

- Agree to
- Also sent by E-Mail

Further services

- Automatic updates → continue
- Location service → enable
- Set up mobile service → set up later in settings
- Screen time → set up later in settings
- Analytics → don't share
- Light or dark display → light

Screenshots on the following slides

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Set Up Mobile Service

You can transfer a phone number from a nearby iPhone or scan a QR code from your network provider.

Transfer From Nearby iPhone >

Use QR Code >

Set Up Later in Settings

No SIM

06:34

Update Your iPhone Automatically

Future software updates will be automatically downloaded and installed for you as they are released. You can manage this in Software Update settings.

Continue

Only Download Automatically

No SIM

15:41

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Screen Time

Get a weekly report with insights about your screen time and set time limits for apps you want to manage. You can also use Screen Time on children's devices and set up parental controls.

Continue

Set Up Later in Settings

Analytics

Help Apple improve its products and services, including Siri and other intelligent features, by allowing analytics of usage and data from your iPhone and iCloud account. You can change your decision later in Settings.

All analysis is performed using privacy preserving techniques such as differential privacy and is not associated with you or your account.

[Learn More...](#)

Share with Apple

Don't Share

[← Back](#)

Light or Dark Display

Select a light or dark appearance and see how iPhone adjusts depending on which one you choose.

Light

Dark

Auto

Continue

Home screen and standard apps

- Notable preinstalled apps by apple
 - Facetime
 - Apple TV
 - Safari Browser (only browser installed)
 - Apple app store
 - Apple maps
 - Apple podcasts
 - iTunes
 - Etc...

First time opening Safari

Screenshots on the following slides

- Google and bing offered on front page
- Upon tapping on search bar: information about personalised suggestions → continue
- First search: dice hhu
 - Asked to accept cookies from google → reject all

Favourites

Privacy Report

 In the last seven days, Safari has prevented 0 trackers from profiling you.

Edit

Safari search now shows personalized suggestions from the web, iTunes, the App Store, movie showtimes, nearby locations, and more.

You can adjust this in Settings. [Learn more...](#)

Continue

Speed up your typing by sliding your finger across the letters to compose a word.

Continue

Done

Siri Suggestions, Search & Privacy

Siri is designed to protect your information and enable you to choose what you share.

Siri Analyses How You Use Your Devices and Apps to Provide Personalised Suggestions and Better Search Results Using Local, On-Device Processing, and Syncs Across Your Devices with End-to-End Encryption Using iCloud

Siri uses local, on-device processing to learn how you use your devices and apps in order to personalise your experience. Using information stored on your device, such as your Safari browsing history, emails, messages, images, notifications and contacts, as well as information donated or contributed by other installed apps, Siri can suggest shortcuts and provide suggestions in searches, share sheet, Calendar, Look Up, Visual Look Up, Safari, apps and more. For example, Siri may use on-device intelligence to suggest who to share a photo with in the share sheet based on who is in the photo. Suggestions may be used to personalise Apple services but are not stored on Apple

 EN Sign in

Before you continue to Google

We use [cookies](#) and data to

- Deliver and maintain Google services
- Track outages and protect against spam, fraud and abuse
- Measure audience engagement and site statistics to understand how our services are used and enhance the quality of those services

If you choose to 'Accept all', we will also use cookies and data to

- Develop and improve new services
- Deliver and measure the effectiveness of ads
- Show personalised content,

 EN Sign in

content and ads can also include more relevant results, recommendations and tailored ads based on past activity from this browser, like previous Google searches. We also use cookies and data to tailor the experience to be age-appropriate, if relevant.

Select 'More options' to see additional information, including details about managing your privacy settings. You can also visit g.co/privacytools at any time.

[Accept all](#)

[Reject all](#)

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 Sign in

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 hhu (Dice)
<https://www.dice.hhu.de>

hhu (Dice)

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[DICELab](#) >

[Trägerschaft](#) >

Default cloud storage: iCloud

- Many apps are by default connected to iCloud

< iCloud Apps using iCloud

- Photos On >
- iCloud Drive On >
- iCloud Mail On >
- Passwords and Keychain On >
- Notes On >
- Messages Off >
- Health On >
- iCloud Calendar On >
- Contacts
- Reminders
- Safari
- Stocks

< iCloud Apps using iCloud

- Stocks
- Home
- Wallet
- Game Center
- Siri
- Freeform
- Books
- Calendar
- FaceTime
- Maps
- Shortcuts

< iCloud Apps using iCloud

- Siri
- Freeform
- Books
- Calendar
- FaceTime
- Maps
- Shortcuts
- Hide My Email >
- Look Me Up >

First time opening App Store

- Allow App Store to use location (location already shown) – allow while using app
- Some recommended apps but no other E-Mail programmes or browsers

Today

26. January

DH

ONLY ON APPLE ARCADE

4 key tips for Hello Kitty Island Adventure

Explore with Hello Kitty and friends

 Apple Arcade
Hello Kitty Island A...
Island adventures await!

Get In-App Purchases

 Royal Match
Ad King Robert's Match 3 Puzzles

Get In-App Purchases

< Apps This Week's Favourites

Planny • Daily Planner
To do list, Focus, Teamwork

Get In-App Purchases

ARD Mediathek
Entertainment

Get

Pok Pok | Preschool Games
Montessori Play for Toddlers

Get In-App Purchases

Gym Workout Alpha Progres...
Weight-lifting Tracker Planner

Get In-App Purchases

StudySmarter: Revision & St...
AI Flashcards, Notes. Homework

Get In-App Purchases

< Apps Must-Have Apps

Picsart Photo Video Editor AI
Image Enhancer & Collage Maker

Get In-App Purchases

TikTok - Videos, Music & LIVE
Watch, discover and stream!

Get In-App Purchases

YouTube: Watch, Listen, Stre...
Videos, Music and Live Streams

Get In-App Purchases

Bumble: Dating & Meet People
Chat, date & make friends app

Get In-App Purchases

LinkedIn: Job Search & News
Network & Find Jobs For You

Get In-App Purchases

First time opening E-Mail

- Protect Mail activity
- Allow notifications
- E-Mail is connected to Apple ID

Attempting to download an App from outside the app store

- Trying to download telegram messenger through chip.de
 - Tapping download forwards into app store
 - „open in Safari“ doesnt work either

Comparison to prior setup in November

- Less preinstalled apps by apple (slide 16)
 - Missing are (for example):
 - GarageBand
 - iMovie
 - Keynotes
- Apple offers information on personalised suggestions (slide 17, 18)

Difference to Set-Up of Google phone

- No Google account needed to be created or to be signed in with which was obligatory when setting up Android and Google phones. However, an Apple ID must be set up, which is not required for the other operating systems.
 - Google services as well as their Privacy and Terms did not have to be accepted.
 - No Personalization settings
- Many pre-installed apps that are provided by Apple itself (Apple tv, Apple podcasts, Apple Maps, iTunes etc.). Also, iCloud is used as default cloud storage, and is connected to many other apps
- Apple does not yet ask permission to interlink between services or offer multiple E-Mails from different providers to be set up like Google does.